

A Prospective Study On Polypharmacy In Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital

Chintha Mohana¹, O Kavya², Reddy Sekhar^{3*}, P.Jenisha Shravani⁴, K.Niharika⁵, J.Bhargavi⁶, K.Purna Sree⁷, T.Sarath Babu⁸

¹Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Krishna Teja Pharmacy college, Tirupati.

^{2,3,4,5,6}Pharm.D Intern, Krishna Teja Pharmacy college, Tirupati.

⁷Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Seshachala College of Pharmacy, Puttur.

⁸Department of Pharmacy Practice, Krishna Teja Pharmacy college, Tirupati.

ABSTRACT

Background: Polypharmacy, the concurrent use of multiple medications, is increasingly prevalent among middle-aged and geriatric populations due to the rise in chronic comorbid conditions. This study aimed to evaluate the prevalence and patterns of polypharmacy, identify associated comorbidities, assess related risk factors, and estimate survival rates using validated clinical scales in a tertiary care hospital setting. **Aims and Objectives:** To assess the burden of comorbid illnesses among middle-aged and elderly patients. To study the association between comorbidities and polypharmacy. To identify risk factors contributing to polypharmacy. To promote awareness regarding comorbidity-driven polypharmacy. To evaluate survival outcomes using the Charlson Comorbidity Index (CCI) and Comorbid Polypharmacy Scale (CPS). **Materials and Methods:** A prospective observational study was conducted over six months (November 2024–April 2025) in the departments of General Medicine, Surgery, Respiratory Medicine, and Orthopedics at Sri Balaji Medical College Hospital, Tirupati. Of 320 screened patients, 72 met the inclusion criteria. Demographic, clinical, and prescription data were collected and analyzed. The number and types of drugs, associated comorbidities, and scores from CCI and CPS were used to evaluate the extent and impact of polypharmacy. **Results:** Among the 72 subjects, 61% were male and the majority (37%) were aged between 60–69 years. Hypertension (89%) and diabetes (67%) were the most common comorbidities. Most patients (67%) had three comorbidities, and 32% were taking six different medications. The most commonly prescribed drug classes were anti-hypertensives (89%) and anti-diabetics (74%). Using the Charlson Comorbidity Index, most patients fell under moderate mortality risk (score 3: 25.4%), with estimated survival rates decreasing as scores increased. Based on the Comorbid Polypharmacy Scale, 79% of patients experienced moderate polypharmacy (score 8–14), while 18% had mild and 3% had severe polypharmacy. **Conclusion:** The study revealed a high prevalence of polypharmacy, particularly among males aged 60–69 years. Hypertension and diabetes were the leading comorbidities. Most patients were under moderate polypharmacy with moderate mortality risk. These findings underscore the need for regular medication reviews, especially in elderly patients with chronic conditions, to mitigate adverse effects and optimize therapeutic outcomes.

Keywords: Polypharmacy.

INTRODUCTION

Polypharmacy is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as "the administration of many drugs at the same time or the administration of an excessive number of drugs"^[1]. Polypharmacy refers to the use of multiple medications, typically five or more. Though definitions vary, it often implies unnecessary or excessive drug use. Common among

older adults, polypharmacy is linked to risks like falls, frailty, and death. Careful medication management is essential to minimize associated health complications^[2]. Although polypharmacy is often seen as problematic, research shows that with proper management and appropriate prescribing, it can reduce hospitalizations. Clinicians must distinguish between harmful over prescribing and necessary, goal-oriented medication use for complex patients^[3].

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Although the term "polypharmacy" is often used broadly to describe various forms of excessive, unnecessary, or inappropriate medication use, different types of polypharmacy can have distinct implications for patients and the healthcare system. The understanding of polypharmacy varies based on its definition, which influences the patient's experience^[4]. Older adults, due to rising chronic and degenerative diseases, are the primary medication users. Around 85% over age 60 experience limited drug effectiveness, leading to the recognition of polypharmacy as a geriatric syndrome^[5].

Polypharmacy types include inappropriate polypharmacy (unnecessary or outdated medications) and appropriate polypharmacy (medications tailored to therapeutic goals). It's classified by quantity: minor (2–4 drugs), major (5+), hyper (10+), and by class, such as same-class polypharmacy, involving multiple drugs from the same category, like two SSRIs^[6]. Polypharmacy, typically defined as the use of five or more medications, is linked to various adverse outcomes in older adults. It increases healthcare costs and the risk of adverse drug events, drug interactions, and medication non-adherence. These can lead to hospitalizations, treatment failure, and disease progression. Polypharmacy is also associated with functional decline, falls, urinary incontinence, and poor nutritional status, all of which reduce quality of life. Each additional medication heightens these risks. Regular medication reviews are essential to minimize harm and ensure safe, effective treatment in older adults dealing with multiple chronic conditions^[7]. Polypharmacy can negatively affect cognitive function, with research indicating that an increased number of medications is a significant risk factor. As the number of prescribed drugs rises, so does the likelihood of cognitive decline, particularly in older adults. Careful medication management is essential to minimize these potential adverse effects^[8]. The causes of polypharmacy arise from complex health conditions, multiple prescribers, and inadequate medication review or coordination^[9]. Lack of shared decision-making can lead to treatment misalignment and non-adherence due to patient preferences^[10]. Comorbidity is the presence of additional diseases alongside a primary condition, commonly termed multiple or multi-morbidity^[11].

The Comorbidity-Polypharmacy Score (CPS) quantifies comorbidities and medications to assess patient health severity across four defined categories. I.e mild (0-7), Moderate(8-14), severe(15-21), Morbid(> or equal to 22)^[12].

The Charlson Comorbidity Index (CCI) is a widely used tool in clinical research to account for comorbidities. It includes 19 conditions linked to increased mortality risk, each assigned weights based on relative risk. Developed in 1987, the CCI remains influential, with over 28,000 citations as of August 2021^[13].

MATERIALS AND METHODS :

It is a Prospective observational study and The study was conducted in departments of Sri balaji medical care hospital(SBMHC), Renigunta, Tirupati .The study was carried out on middle aged and geriatric patients (Above 40 age group) of either sex for a period of 6 months from December2024 to May 2025.

A total of 72 subjects of all departments were enrolled in the study after evaluating for inclusion and exclusion criteria. The purpose of the study was explained and written informed consent was obtained from all the participants .Middle Age and geriatrics (Above 40 years age group) with co-morbid illness associated with polypharmacy, Patients prescribed greater than 1 or equal to 1 medication in Chronic comorbid condition are included in the study. Patients who are not willing to participate in this study, Middle age and geriatrics without co morbidities, The patients who are receiving acute treatment in co morbid condition, Middle age and Geriatric patients who are receiving chemotherapy were excluded in the study. For the collection of the data, the case record files of all the patients admitted in the departments were thoroughly reviewed each day during the study period.

The information recorded included the demographic details of the patients, co-morbid illness, details about medications being used. The co-morbid condition associated with polypharmacy were assessed by using charlson co-morbid index and co-morbid polypharmacy score. The data were stored in the Microsoft excel and were analyzed by using the mean \pm standard deviation.

RESULTS :

The demographic details and characteristics of the patients indicate a male predominance, with 44 out of 72 subjects (61%) being male and 28 (39%) females. The most common age group was 60–69 years, comprising 27 patients (37%), followed by the 50–59 age group with 17 patients (24%). The 40–49 and 70–79 age groups each had 14% of the patients (10 subjects), while those above 80 years accounted for 6% (4 subjects). Regarding the number of medications used, polypharmacy was prevalent, with 32% (23 subjects) taking 6 medications, 28% (20

subjects) taking 5 medications, and 21% (15 subjects) taking 7 medications. Additionally, 8% (6 subjects) took 8 medications, 6% (4 subjects) took 4 medications, 3% (2 subjects) took 9 medications, and 1% (1 subject each) took either 10 or 12 medications. In terms of comorbidities, most patients had three comorbid conditions (48 subjects), followed by two (14 subjects), four (9 subjects), and five (1 subject). The patient demographics show a male predominance (61%) and a peak age range of 60-69 years (36%). Polypharmacy is common, with 32% taking 6 medications. Most patients have 3 comorbidities (48) [Table 1].

Table 1. Demographic Details and Characteristics of Patients

S.NO	DETAILS	CHARACTERISTICS	NO. OF SUBJECTS (%)
1.	GENDER	MALE FEMALE	44(61%) 28(39%)
2.	AGE	40-49 AGE GROUP 50-59 AGE GROUP 60-69 AGE GROUP 70-79 AGE GROUP > 80 AGE GROUP	14(19%) 17(24%) 27(37%) 10(14%) 4(6%)
3.	NUMBER OF MEDICATIONS USED BY SUBJECTS	QUADRUPLE DRUG QUINTUPLE DRUG SEXTUPLE DRUG SEPTUPLE DRUG OCTUPLE DRUG NONUPLE DRUG DECUPLE DRUG DUODECUPLE DRUG	4(6%) 20(28%) 23(32%) 15(21%) 6(8%) 2(3%) 1(1%) 1(1%)
4.	COMORBIDITS	TWO THREE FOUR FIVE	14(19%) 48(67%) 9(12%) 1(1%)

Class of drugs used by the subjects Anti-Hypertensives: 64 (89%) and Anti Diabetic drugs: 53 (74%), Bronchodilators: 28 (39%), Corticosteroids: 27 (37%), Anti-Thyroid drugs: 14 (19%), Anti-Platelet drugs: 8 (11%), Statins: 17 (24%), Anti-Gastrointestinal drugs: 10 (14%), Anti-Epileptics: 1 (1%), Antirheumatic: 1 (1%). The most commonly

administered medications Anti-Hypertensive: 89% [Table 2].

Charlson Comorbidity Index scores showed that only 1 subject (1.8%) had a score of 0, indicating a 100% survival rate. Scores of 1 and 2 were seen in 10 (18.1%) and 11 (20%) subjects, with survival rates of 96% and 90%, respectively. Moderate risk (score 3)

was most common in 14 subjects (25.4%), with a 77% survival rate. Ten subjects (18.1%) had a score of 4 (53% survival), seven (12.7%) had 5 (21% survival), and two (3.6%) had 6, with only a 2% survival rate. Survival declined as scores increased [Table 8]. Among the subjects, 13 (18%) had mild polypharmacy (score 0–7), while the majority, 57

(79%), fell under moderate polypharmacy (score 8–14). Only 2 subjects (3%) experienced severe polypharmacy (score 15–21), and none were in the morbid category (score >21). This distribution suggests that most individuals were on a moderate number of medications, with very few at the mild or severe extremes [Table 3].

Table 6. 2: Details of Classes of Drug

SNO	DISEASE	CLASSIFICATION	NO. OF SUBJECTS	(%)
1	DIABETES	A) GLIFLOZINS B) BIGUANIDES C)SULPHONYL UREAS D)SGLT ₂ INHIBITORS E) DPP4 INHIBITORS	48	67
2	HYPERTENSION	A) ARBS B) DIURETICS C)BETA- BLOCKERS D)CALCIUM CHANNEL BLOCKERS E) ACE INHIBITORS F) ALPHA-BLOCKER	63	87
3	OAD	A) BRONCHODILATORS B) INHALER C)CORTICOSTEROIDS	27	37
4	THYROID	A) ANTI-THYROID DRUGS B) THYROID DRUGS	15	21
5	CAD	A) ANTI-PLATELET B)STATINS	12	17
6	DYSLIPIDEMIA	A)HMG-CoA REDUCTASE INHIBITORS B)FIBRATES	12	17
7	CKD	A) ANTI-HYPERTENSIVES B)ALKALISING AGENTS	5	7
8	GASTROINTESTINAL DISEASE	A) DIGESTIVE ENYMES B)H2 RECEPTOR BLOCKER	10	14
9	RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS	A) NON-BIOLOGICAL DMARDS B) TRICYCLIC ANTIDEPRESSANTS C)NSAIDS	2	3

		D)ORAL CORTICOSTEROIDS		
10	SEIZURES	A) BENZIDIAZEPINES B) PYRROLIDINE C)IMINOSTILBENE	2	3
11	LICHENOID DERMATITIS	ANTI-INFECTIVE	1	1
12	OSTEOARTHIRITIS	NSAIDS	1	1
13	POLYARTHRALGIA	NSAIDS	1	1

Table 3: Charlson Comorbidity Index

SNO	CHARLSON COMORBID CONDITION	NO.OF SUBJECTS (%)	ESTIMATE D SURVIVAL RATE	COMORBID POLY PHARMACY SCALE	NO. OF SUBJECT S (%)
1	LOW MORTALITY RISK: 0 POINTS	1(1%)	100%	MILD (0-7)	13(18%)
	1 POINTS	11(15%)	96%		
	2 POINTS	11(15%)	90%		
2	MODERATE MORTALITY RISK: 3 POINTS	23(32%)	77%	MODERATE (8-14)	57(79%)
	4 POINTS	14(19%)	53%	SEVERE(15-21)	2(3%)
	5 POINTS	8(11%)	21%		
3	HIGH MORTALITY RISK: 6 POINTS	4(5%)	2%	MORBID(>21)	0(0%)
TOTAL		72		72	100

DISCUSSION

This study assessed the prevalence of poly pharmacy among 320 middle-aged and elderly patients in a tertiary care hospital over six months. Poly pharmacy was observed in 72 patients (22.5%), indicating a significant presence. Among these, 44 were males and 28 females, with the highest prevalence in the 60–69 age group. These findings support previous research, including Rohini Gupta et al. (2018), which noted increased poly pharmacy in the elderly due to a higher burden of chronic diseases. The study found most

patients experienced major poly pharmacy (six or more drugs), with some reaching hyperpoly pharmacy (ten or more). This is concerning due to increased risks of drug interactions and non-adherence, as widely reported in literature. These findings align with studies by Minal B, Chacko S, Jaya S, Rajesh P, George G, and others. Around 50% of patients reported no personal habits like smoking, alcohol, or tobacco use. Though less prevalent, these habits contribute to chronic disease progression and should be addressed in care plans, supporting findings by Reeve E et al.

This study highlights the clinical and public health need for regular medication reviews, particularly in elderly patients with multiple comorbidities. Inappropriate medication use can be reduced through clinical pharmacist involvement, deprescribing protocols, and patient education. Tools like the Charlson Comorbidity Index (CCI) and Comorbid Polypharmacy Scale (CPS) aid in safer prescribing. Notably, only 1.8% of patients had a CCI of 0, while 32% scored 3, indicating moderate mortality risk. CPS data showed 79% had moderate polypharmacy. These findings align with studies by Masnoon N, Shakib S, Kalisch-Ellett L, and Caughey GE.

CONCLUSION

Among 72 subjects, poly pharmacy was more common in males (44), with the highest prevalence in the 60–69 age group (26 participants), highlighting older adults' vulnerability. Notably, 35 had no personal habits, and 23 were on six or more medications, indicating a significant medication burden. Hypertension was the most frequent comorbidity (53 cases). CCI analysis showed 23 had moderate mortality risk, while CPS indicated 53 had moderate comorbid poly pharmacy. These findings stress the importance of regular medication reviews, especially in older males with chronic illnesses, to reduce drug-related risks and improve care. Such patterns are common in patients with chronic conditions, highlighting the need for careful medication management to prevent drug interactions. A decreasing survival rate is observed with rising Charlson scores, with the highest patient count at a score of 3.

REFERENCES

1. Dona Varghese; cecilia Ishida; Preeti patel ; hayas haseer koya, et al polypharmacy, 2024

2. mahin Delara, auren murray, Prevalence and factors associated with Polypharmacy: a systematic review and meta-analysis, 2022
3. Ali Elbeddini, polypharmacy-an overview 2023,
4. Seyede Salehe Mortazavi¹, Mohsen shati²; Defining polypharmacy in the Elderly; a systematic review protocol 2016
5. Erick mercado Ramirez, carlos alberto cotenna alcaraz, prevalence of Polypharmacy and interaction in older adults in primary care 2018
6. Monegat M, Sermet C. Polypharmacy: Definitions, measurement and stakes involved review of the literature amh measurement tests, questions d' economie de la sante . -2014 dec
7. Robert Maher Jr, Clinical Consequences of Polypharmacy in Elderly 2014.
8. George Doumat, The effect of polypharmacy on healthcare services utilization in older adults with comorbidities: a retrospective cohort study 2023.
9. Scottish Government Model of care polypharmacy working Groups Polypharmacy guidance. Second edition 2015
10. Pistons C and wright H. Keeping patients safe when they transfer between care providers- getting the medicines right. Royal pharmaceutical society. 2012
11. Christopher Harrison, Comorbidity versus multimorbidity :2021 .
12. Stanislaw P Stawicki¹, Sarathi Kalra² Comorbidity polypharmacy score and its clinical utility: A pragmatic practitioner's perspective
13. Allison Drosdowsky¹, The Charlson Comorbidity Index: problems with use in epidemiological research.

HOW TO CITE: Chintha Mohana, O Kavya, Reddy Sekhar, P. Jenisha Shrivani, K. Niharika, J. Bhargavi, K. Purna Sree, T. Sarath Babu, A Prospective Study On Polypharmacy In Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital, J. Pharm. Sci., 2026, 2 (6), 363-368. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20738312>

